

Studies on Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some New Chalcones, Flavones and Flavonols

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The present communication reports the synthesis of some new chalcones, flavones and flavonols expecting their enhanced antimicrobial activity. Different substituted hydroxyacetophenone on treatment with 4-chloro-1-naphthaldehyde in presence of alcoholic potassium hydroxide and subsequent acidification, yielded¹ chalcones (1a-i). Seven of them (1a-g) having a hydroxyl at 2'-position when refluxed with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol gave² the corresponding flavones (2a-g). The flavonols (3a-g) were prepared³ from the respective 2'-hydroxychalcones (2a-g) by treatment with alkaline hydrogen peroxide and subsequent acidification.

All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity against *Curvularia lunata* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* following the disc-diffusion⁴ and hanging-drop⁵ methods.

The results of inhibition were found to be significant (Table 1). The hydroxychalcones were found to be more inhibitory against both the bacteria

and fungi, but flavonols were found to be most inhibitory in action than the corresponding chalcones and flavones.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-3

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Antibacterial		Antifungal			
			Dia of inhibition zone (mm)		<i>C. lunata</i>		<i>H. oryzae</i>	
			<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	Germi-nation %	Germ tube length (μ)	Germi-nation %	Germ tube length (μ)
1a	2'-OH	145	Nil	Nil	100	230	100	250
b	2'-OH-5'-CH ₃	162	28	Nil	100	192	100	400
c	2'-OH-5'-Cl	189	Nil	Nil	100	400	100	400
d	2'-OH-5'-Br	176	42	Nil	80	192	100	480
e	2'-OH-4'-CH ₃ -5'-Cl	183	44	Nil	80	160	60	400
f	2'-OH-3',5'-di-Cl	191	38	15	60	120	40	200
g	2'-OH-3',5'-di-I	214	28	26	70	180	50	240
h	4'-OH	243	36	28	30	240	85	80
i	4' OH-3',5'-di-I	245	16	14	60	80	100	240
2a	H	207	Nil	Nil	100	340	100	320
b	6-CH ₃	189	45	22	80	80	100	320
c	6-Cl	221	18	10	10	40	40	80
d	6-Br	220	15	14	50	80	20	40
e	6-Cl-7-CH ₃	215	25	13	80	170	75	200
f	6,8-di-Cl	289	24	10	70	128	60	150
g	6,8-di-I	273	40	26	35	70	30	80
3a	H	243	Nil	Nil	100	250	100	240
b	6-CH ₃	276	34	15	50	80	60	64
c	6-Cl	263	20	01	70	95	80	80
d	6-Br	255	12	Nil	100	250	100	160
e	6-Cl-7-CH ₃	270	19	12	90	280	90	340
f	6,8-di-Cl	310	20	12	05	32	10	60
g	6,8-di-I	337	37	18	10	40	20	15
Choloromycetin			48	25				
Water-ethanol (9 : 1, v/v)					95 0	320	95 0	400

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